

Comparison of hydrothermal carbonization and torrefaction of azolla biomass: Analysis of the solid products

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ABSTRACT

The effect of torrefaction and hydrothermal carbonization has been studied on *Azolla filiculoides*, which is a potential aquatic biomass feedstock for renewable energy sources. Hydrochar and torrefied azolla samples were prepared at three temperatures (260, 280, 300 °C) with 15 min residence time. The thermal behavior and the volatile content of the raw and thermally treated biomass samples were determined by thermogravimetric analysis, while the detailed composition of the volatile contents was analyzed by pyrolysis-gas chromatography/mass spectrometry (Py-GC/MS). The major pyrolysis products were phenolic compounds, monocyclic and condensed aromatic hydrocarbons, nitrogen heterocycles, nitriles, carbohydrate decomposition products, phytosterols, and fatty acid derivatives. Principal component analysis on Py-GC/MS data revealed that the pyrolyzates of the samples differed significantly depending on the temperature and type of pretreatment. Hydrothermal carbonization resulted in more severe decomposition at each temperature than torrefaction. The volatile content of torrefied azolla decreased gradually with torrefaction temperature, while 280 °C was a sufficient temperature to remove the majority of the volatile content during HTC. The amounts of phytosterols decreased to the highest extent during both treatments. The thermally less stable carbohydrate components of azolla were decomposed during torrefaction, while hydrothermal carbonization affected other constituents of the biomass (e.g., proteins), as well. During pyrolysis, the formation of aromatic compounds (phenol, benzene, pyridine, and pyrrole derivatives) was more favored from hydrochars than from torrefied azolla.

1. Introduction

The usage of biofuels offers an alternative solution for reducing the global greenhouse gas emissions by partially substituting fossil fuels. Generally, the utilization of biomass as a fuel source is limited by some disadvantageous physical and chemical properties like low heating value, low energy density, high moisture content, high O/C ratio, and biodegradability. These properties are resulting in high transportation and handling costs, limited storage lifetime, and less effective direct combustion [1]. However, low-temperature dry or wet thermal treatments are able to improve these disadvantageous properties of raw biomass.

Torrefaction is a dry thermochemical conversion process performed in a temperature range of 200–300 °C under an inert atmosphere at ambient pressure. It is useful for biomass with moisture content below 15%, otherwise a previous drying process is needed. During heating, an

initial mass loss occurs at around 100 °C by releasing the moisture content; however, extractives and smaller molecules formed by the scission of the most labile functional groups of the macromolecules are evolved at higher temperature. The extent of the overall mass loss is typically moderate. The major product of torrefaction is the solid torrefied material; in addition, an oily liquid of condensable compounds and gases are also released [2,3].

Hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) is a wet thermal process performed in the presence of subcritical water at an elevated temperature (180–300 °C) and pressure (above 1 MPa). The applied pressure and residence time vary in a broader range; however, a shorter residence time is used usually than during torrefaction. The presence of liquid water is advantageous because it promotes the thermal decomposition by hydrolysis, and it decreases the amount of salts and minerals in biomass by leaching [4]. Therefore, a solid product with lower ash content is formed during hydrothermal carbonization, which in turn

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means enhanced fuel properties [2]. HTC results in a solid product with a similar mass yield, energy content, and higher heating value (HHV) at much lower temperatures than torrefaction [1]. Beside the solid hydrochar, gases and two liquid phases, a crude bio-oil and a water phase, are formed. HTC as a pretreatment is also advantages in terms of bio-oil production by subsequent pyrolysis, as the hydrothermal carbonization reduces the yield of acidic light volatiles and decreases the nitrogen content considerably, which improves the stability of the pyrolysis oil [5].

Both dry and wet thermal treatments have some advantages and disadvantages depending on the applied technological setup. Both methods produce a more homogenous solid biomass fuel with higher energy density, enhanced durability, and decreased hygroscopic properties. Regarding the elemental composition, both types of thermal treatments reduce the ratios of *H/C* and *O/C* of biomass by carbonization [2,6,7]. HTC is especially favorable if the biomass contains high amount of moisture, as no drying process is required. The char produced by HTC contains less ash, which is advantageous for some applications. Moreover, for attaining the same char yield, lower temperature is required in the case of HTC comparing to torrefaction [8]. However, the design of high-pressure reactor and the continuous operation have yet some issues to be solved for larger scale hydrothermal conversion [9,10], while torrefaction is a simpler and more mature technology.

The renewable feedstock for producing biofuels can be obtained from various types of biomass. Aquatic plants (e.g., algae) represent feedstock materials for the so-called third-generation biofuels, which are getting much attention nowadays. Aquatic plants have higher growing rates and different cultivation technologies than lignocellulosic plants; hence, the production of such biomass does not compete for arable land with crops for food [11–13]. Therefore, azolla is a promising candidate for cultivation as a third-generation biofuel feedstock and energy source [14–16].

The species of azolla are macrophytes of lakes and wetlands with a high growing rate, widespread on the moderate and tropical regions of both the Northern and Southern Hemispheres [17]. This aquatic plant lives with a cyanobacterium symbiont within the cavities of its leaves, which enables it to grow freely in the upper layers of water bodies by fixation of the atmospheric nitrogen [18]. For sustainable agriculture, the accumulated elemental nitrogen of azolla provides a proper source of essential nutrients as a biofertilizer (e.g., as a dual crop in the cultivation of rice) [19–21]. Azolla is also suitable for bioremediation [22] and accumulation of organic [23,24] or heavy metal pollutants [25–28]. The plant can also grow on marginal areas, and even on wastewater [29,30], so the cultivation of azolla can help the utilization of polluted water bodies and provides an energy feedstock. The review article of Kollah et al. [31] presents numerous studies describing the usefulness of azolla production in more details, especially in terms of agricultural and environmental aspects.

The main constituents of azolla are carbohydrates (cellulose, hemicellulose, and starch), lipids, and microalgal components (due to the cyanobacterial symbiont) [30]; however, it does not contain lignin, but polyphenolic constituents [32]. The chemical composition of azolla makes it a suitable feedstock for solid fuel production by both pyrolysis and HTC [30,33–36]. Due to the high moisture content of the aquatic plant, azolla, HTC seems an obvious choice for energetic utilization, while torrefaction is a simpler, more mature technology. In the literature, there is a lack of comparative studies on torrefaction and HTC of azolla or any other aquatic plants.

The goal of this study was to reveal and compare the effects of torrefaction and HTC on *Azolla filiculoides* by characterization of the solid products formed during dry and wet thermal treatments at the same reaction temperatures. The composition of the volatile products of the char samples was studied in detail with the aim of understanding the nature and the severity of the carbonization processes. The

morphological changes on the surface of chars were monitored by scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

The raw biomass, *Azolla filiculoides* (mosquito fern, Salviniaceae family) was sampled by RMIT University, Australia from the tropical regions of Australia [30]. The sample was oven-dried after sampling, milled, and then shipped for the thermal experiments.

2.1.1. Preparation of torrefied azolla chars

The torrefaction experiments were performed in a TGS-2 thermobalance (Perkin-Elmer, Inc., USA) used with a modified furnace and a Eurotherm temperature controller (Worthing, UK). An aliquot of 8–10 mg azolla biomass was treated thermally in a platinum pan under argon atmosphere using a gas flow rate of 140 mL min⁻¹. The torrefaction temperatures of 260, 280 and 300 °C were attained at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ and the sample was maintained at the set temperature for 15 min. The names of torrefied azolla samples are abbreviated and labelled with the temperature of thermal pretreatment: Tor260, Tor280, Tor300.

2.1.2. Preparation of hydrochars

The hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) experiments were performed in a 100 mL high-pressure autoclave (4560 micro reactor, Parr Instrument Co., USA) at different temperatures (260, 280, and 300 °C). The reactor was loaded with azolla and an abundant excess of water (1:6 by weight), then it was purged with nitrogen to flush out the air. The reactants were stirred, heated up to the desired temperature in auto mode (heating rate: 8–10 °C min⁻¹) and kept there for 15 min. The pressure was autogenous and was in the range of 60–83 bar maximum. After removing the heater, water was used for cooling (30–45 min). After cooling down, the gaseous products were vented and the liquid portion was separated from the solid residue using diethyl ether and vacuum filtration. The solid products were extracted with acetone in a Soxhlet apparatus until the solvent in the thimble became colorless. The acetone insoluble fraction was dried at 80 °C then weighed, and called as solid residue. This method is based on our earlier work on HTC reaction optimization of water hyacinth biomass [37]. More details about the applied HTC method can be found in the paper of Miranda et al. [30]. The names of azolla hydrochar samples are abbreviated and labelled with the temperature of hydrothermal carbonization: HTC260, HTC280, HTC300.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

The TGA measurements were carried out by using the modified Perkin-Elmer TGS-2 thermobalance, which has a resolution of 0.1 µg. Approximately 4 mg samples were analyzed in argon atmosphere with a flow rate of 140 mL min⁻¹. The samples were heated at a rate of 20 °C min⁻¹ from 25 to 900 °C in a platinum sample pan. The amount of residue represents the pyrolysis char yield and the volatile content was calculated by the difference between the initial and final masses at 50 and 900 °C.

The ash content of the carbonized residues was determined by oxidation of the charred samples in the thermobalance. The charred residue was heated from room temperature up to 900 °C at a rate of 20 °C min⁻¹ while purging the thermobalance by synthetic air with a flow rate of 140 mL min⁻¹. The amount of residue after combustion represents the ash content and the fixed carbon content was calculated by the difference between the initial and final masses at 50 and 900 °C.

Baseline corrections of the TG curves were taken into account

during data processing. The baseline was determined with empty sample holder under the same conditions as the experiments with samples and the baseline was subtracted from the measured TG curves. The repeatability of TG curves is presented in Fig. S1 of Supplementary data. The relative standard deviation of char yield data calculated from five parallel experiments is 0.6%.

2.2.2. Pyrolysis-gas chromatography/mass spectrometry (Py-GC/MS)

The Py-GC/MS measurements were performed by using a Pyroprobe 2000 pyrolyzer (CDS Analytical, Oxford, USA) interfaced to an Agilent 6890A/5973 GC/MS system (Agilent Technologies, Inc., Santa Clara, USA). The samples of about 1.2 mg were weighed into a quartz tube and pyrolyzed at 600 °C for 20 s under helium atmosphere inside the pyrolyzer chamber maintained at 280 °C. The pyrolysis products were flushed by helium onto the GC column using a flow rate of 20 mL min⁻¹ and a split ratio of 20:1. The pyrolysis products were separated on a DB-1701 capillary column (30 m × 0.25 mm, 0.25 μm film thickness). The heating program of the GC oven started at 40 °C, held for 4 min, then the temperature increased at a rate of 6 °C min⁻¹ to 280 °C with an isothermal period of 16 min. A mass range of 14–500 Da was scanned by the mass selective detector in an electron impact mode at 70 eV. The identification of the molecules was based on NIST11 and Wiley09 mass spectral libraries, and literature data [38–40]. The experiments were carried out in duplicates on each sample. The relative standard deviation of peak integrals was 9.1% for the peaks of a relative intensity ≥ 1%, while it was 10.7% for the whole data set.

2.2.3. Principal component analysis (PCA)

For pattern visualization of the Py-GC/MS results, PCA was used as a chemometric tool [41], which reveals correlations and differences among the solid samples characterized by their thermal decomposition products. Generally, PCA transforms the original variables into new variables called principal components (factors). Each factor is uncorrelated (orthogonal) and is a linear combination of the original variables. The first principal component accounts for the maximum of total variance; the second is uncorrelated with the first and accounts for the maximum of residual variance, and so on. The results can be presented in a score plot and a loading plot. The values, which denote the samples in the space defined by the principal components, are the component scores. Factor loadings (of each principal component) present the correlation between the original variables and the factors.

2.2.4. Inductively coupled plasma–optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES)

The ashing of 2 g biomass was carried out in a furnace at 550 °C according to the CEN/TS 14775:2004 standard method. The ash samples of 40–45 mg were weighed into the Teflon tubes of the Anton-Paar

Microwave 3000 sample preparation system. Aliquots of 8 mL nitric acid (65%, Suprapur) and 0.5 mL hydrofluoric acid (38%, a.r.) were added to each sample and the digestion program was completed as follows: heating up to 200 °C in 25 min, holding it for 25 min at 20 bar pressure, then cooling down. After this process, 8 mL of saturated boric acid solution (6%) was added to the samples to bind the free fluoride ions and the whole digestion program was repeated. The solutions were measured with Spectro Genesis ICP-OES with axial plasma observation. The measurements were triplicated. The ICP instrument was calibrated with multi-element standard solutions purchased from Molar Chemicals Ltd.

2.2.5. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

The morphology of the samples was studied with a Zeiss EVO40 scanning electron microscope. The samples for SEM were dispersed on an adhesive coated carbon paper and then were gold coated. Considering the electron beam sensibility of the samples, we used the tungsten hairpin filament at 5 kV. To get information on the morphology, secondary electron images were acquired at different magnifications, but the micrographs are presented at 2000× magnification in this paper.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Thermal decomposition monitored by thermogravimetry

3.1.1. Characterization of raw azolla

The thermal decomposition properties of the solid samples were evaluated by thermogravimetric measurements. The thermogravimetric (TG) and derivative thermogravimetric curves (DTG) show in Fig. 1 that the dried raw azolla sample started to release its volatile content at around 140 °C and decomposed mainly in the temperature range of 200–400 °C (the major peak of DTG curve). However, a remarkable part of the sample degraded between 400 and 550 °C resulting in a shoulder on the DTG curve. According to TGA, relatively high amount of char (32.6%) was formed during heating up to 900 °C. The char consists of carbon residue (called fixed carbon) and inorganic material (determined as ash). The ash content was measured by burning the organic components of char in oxidative atmosphere. The proximate analysis data are found in Table 1. The thermal behavior of azolla was similar to the thermal decomposition pattern of algae [42]. In addition, the proximate analysis data in Table 1 showed that volatile matter (VM) and fixed carbon (FC) contents of azolla were more similar to that of macroalgae than that of lignocellulosic biomass [43,44].

The inorganic content of azolla biomass was determined by ashing the sample at 550 °C resulting in relatively high ash (10.8%, dry basis).

Fig. 1. TG and DTG curves of raw azolla, (a) torrefied samples (Tor260, Tor280, Tor300), and (b) hydrochars (HTC260, HTC280, HTC300). Solid yields of pre-treatment as initial percentages are marked with dashed lines.

Table 1
Original and derived proximate analysis data of raw azolla, torrefied samples, and hydrochars, and the solid yields of thermal pretreatments.

	Content (%)	Raw azolla	Torrefied samples			Hydrochars		
			Tor260	Tor280	Tor300	HTC260	HTC280	HTC300
Proximate analysis ^a	Volatile matter (VM)	67.4	60.5	55.5	50.4	47.7	44.1	39.4
	Pyrolysis char	32.6	39.5	44.5	49.6	52.3	55.9	60.6
	Fixed carbon (FC)	23.9	28.3	32.4	36.5	43.1	46.0	49.6
	Ash	8.7	11.2	12.1	13.1	9.3	9.9	11.0
Solid yield of pretreatment (%)	–	83.8	75.2	67.1	66.8 ^b	38.0 ^b	33.8 ^b	
Derived quantities ^c	Volatile matter (VM _{der})	67.4	50.7	41.8	33.8	31.9	16.8	13.3
	Pyrolysis char (Char _{der})	32.6	33.1	33.4	33.3	35.0	21.2	20.5
	Fixed carbon (FC _{der})	23.9	23.8	24.3	24.5	28.8	17.5	16.8
	Ash (Ash _{der})	8.7	9.4	9.1	8.8	6.2	3.8	3.7

^a Dry basis.

^b The solid yields of hydrochars are according to Miranda et al. [30].

^c Corrected by the mass loss occurred during thermal pretreatment.

The elemental analysis of the ash was performed by ICP-OES. The alkali (Na, K) and alkaline earth metal (Ca, Mg) ions constituted about one third of the total ash content. The amounts of the elements phosphorus, silicon, and sulfur were also significant (ca. 0.5% each) beside the contents of other important metals (e.g., Fe, Al, Mn). Heavy metals (e.g., Cd, Cr, Hg, Mo, Sn) were only present in trace amounts or under the detection limit. The detailed inorganic composition of azolla is presented in Table S1 of Supplementary data.

3.1.2. Thermal decomposition of torrefied samples

The thermal decomposition behavior of the torrefied samples (Tor260, Tor280, Tor300) and the oven-dried raw azolla sample is compared in Fig. 1a. The proximate analysis data determined from the thermogravimetric experiments are listed in Table 1. During torrefaction, a part of the volatile content was released, so the VM of torrefied samples was reduced, while the relative amounts of FC and ash were increased (Table 1, Proximate analysis). In order to reveal the changes of solid materials due to torrefaction more clearly, the initial sample amounts of TG curves were corrected by the mass loss occurred during the torrefaction pretreatment and the data calculated this way are called derived quantities (Table 1). For example, azolla released 16.2% volatile matter and yielded 83.8% solid residue during torrefaction at 260 °C (Table 1, Solid yield of pretreatment). Therefore, the rescaled TG curve of Tor260 sample starts at 83.8% in Fig. 1a. During TGA experiment, Tor260 sample released 50.7% volatile products calculated on the original mass base (Table 1, VM_{der}), so leaving behind 33.1% char (Table 1, Char_{der}). Similarly, the DTG curves of the torrefied samples were rescaled taking into account the previous mass loss. Thus, the changes in the treated biomass samples during thermal decomposition became apparently more comparable.

The thermogravimetric curves in Fig. 1a reveal that the volatile components were released partially and the moieties of low thermal stability were decomposed during torrefaction. The biomass decomposed gradually with the rising temperature of torrefaction. However, each torrefied sample produced similar amount of charred residue by TGA (calculated on the basis of the initial amount of biomass prior to torrefaction) than the raw biomass did by direct slow pyrolysis (Table 1, Char_{der}). Likewise, the FC content of torrefied samples was retained also after the thermal pretreatment. Therefore, torrefaction as a pretreatment did not affect the gross char yield in further pyrolysis; it decreased only the volatile formation from azolla. In the case of the Tor300 sample, the volatile content (VM_{der}) was reduced to the half of the initial amount. This observation suggests that the thermal decomposition of the rest of the biomass proceeded via similar mechanisms after torrefaction than the pyrolysis of the raw biomass did.

The results of oxidative TGA measurements of the char residues indicated that the ash content of azolla biomass (8.7%) did not change appreciably by torrefaction (Table 1, Ash_{der}). This observation is

confirmed by other torrefaction studies on various types of biomass (e.g., willow, pinewood, rice husk, peanut husk, bagasse) [45–47].

3.1.3. Thermal decomposition of hydrochars

As the solid yield data show in Table 1, a large part of the thermally less stable components was removed during HTC. At as low a temperature as 260 °C, the solid yield was 66.8%, i.e., 33.2% material was removed. At 280 °C, the solid yield of HTC further reduced to 38.0%, while increasing the temperature to 300 °C, the solid yield decreased only to 33.8%. The original proximate analysis results of hydrochars, calculated from thermogravimetric data, are presented in Table 1. The VM of the samples was reduced remarkably by HTC, while the relative amounts of char, including both FC and ash, were increased. The TG and DTG curves of azolla hydrochars (HTC260, HTC280, and HTC300) are shown in Fig. 1b in comparison to the curves of the raw sample. The curves were rescaled similarly as in the case of torrefied samples; i.e., the value of the relative initial mass of TG curves were corrected by the mass loss occurred during hydrothermal carbonization (See solid yield data in Table 1). The derived quantities calculated this way give a deeper insight into the effect of HTC process on the composition of hydrochars.

It is known that the decomposition rate of the cellulosic content of biomass increases rapidly during HTC above 250 °C [7]. The small DTG peak of the main decomposition stage at 300–400 °C can be related to the degradation of the carbohydrate content remained after HTC at 260 °C of azolla. This DTG peak was strongly reduced in the cases of HTC280 and HTC300 samples. Comparing to raw azolla, the devolatilization rate of HTC260 sample did not change between 400 and 600 °C. However, the other two hydrochar samples show strongly reduced DTG peaks in this temperature range indicating that severe decomposition occurred in all major components of azolla during HTC at 280 and 300 °C. The comparison of the DTG curves of HTC and torrefied samples shows that the maximum rate of decomposition is significantly lower in the case of HTC samples indicating more severe degradation during HTC. The DTG peak at 300–400 °C associated with the decomposition of the carbohydrate content of HTC260 sample is much smaller than that of Tor300 sample pointing to the extensive degradation of the HTC sample.

As the derived quantities show in Fig. 1b and Table 1, HTC260 sample provided a slightly higher amount of char residue calculated for the initial dry mass of azolla than the raw sample. On the other hand, about 30% of the ash content (2.5% on initial dry basis) was removed by the liquid phase during HTC at 260 °C (Table 1, Ash_{der}). So the increased char content is due to the increased FC_{der} content, which might be explained by the effect of high pressure enhancing the condensation of the radicals during degradation.

The thermal decomposition of HTC280 and HTC300 hydrochars produced much less char_{der} residue than HTC260, which suggests

significant changes of the impact of HTC on the biomass above 260 °C. It is in agreement with the different decomposition pattern of hydrochars, as discussed above (See DTG curves in Fig. 1b). According to the ash content analysis, more than a half of the inorganic components were removed by the solvent medium at 280 and 300 °C during HTC procedure (Table 1, Ash_{der}). Thus, the rigorous conditions were tending to decompose the organic and dissolve the inorganic components of the biomass to a high ratio. However, the thermal characterization of HTC280 and HTC300 samples revealed (Fig. 1b) that there was not much difference between the overall effects of HTC at the two highest working temperatures applied. Thus, 280 °C is a sufficient temperature to remove the majority of the decomposing materials in the subcritical aqueous medium. As the DTG curves illustrate, HTC280 and HTC300 samples have high thermal stability decomposing mainly in the temperature range of 400–500 °C.

The comparison of the effect of torrefaction and HTC reveals that HTC resulted in a much higher degree of conversion of the solid mass than torrefaction (Table 1). During HTC, 2–2.5 times more materials were removed from azolla than during torrefaction performed at the same temperature. Hydrothermal carbonization at 260 °C resulted in a slightly higher conversion than torrefaction at 300 °C. The bigger efficiency of HTC can be due to the hydrolyzing and dissolving effect of water and the high pressure. As a consequence of the different conversions, the VM content of hydrochars is much lower and the relative amount of pyrolysis char is much higher than that of the torrefied samples. The original proximate analysis data show that the ratio of ash content increased only slightly (up to 11.0%) despite of the relatively high conversion rate of the hydrothermal process; contrary to the torrefied samples (up to 13.1%). The Ash_{der} data reveal (Table 1) that significant amount of ash was removed during HTC, while the Ash_{der} content was practically unchanged during torrefaction. It can be explained by the considerable leaching effect of the water media during the hydrothermal carbonization of biomass dissolving a part of the inorganic components [48].

3.2. Characterization of sample morphology by SEM

The changes of the surface morphological structure as a result of torrefaction and HTC was inspected using scanning electron microscopy

(SEM) technique. The SEM image of the raw material, torrefied samples and hydrochars are visible in Fig. 2. The images reveal highly different morphological changes comparing the torrefied azolla samples and hydrochars. As a result of torrefaction, cracks and fractures appeared in Tor260 sample, which became more intense in Tor280 sample. Higher torrefaction temperature (300 °C) resulted in the formation of pores and led to a spongy structure of Tor300. The structure of the azolla sample was destructed more severely as a result of HTC at 260 °C (HTC260) comparing to Tor300. Increasing the HTC temperature did not cause further significant visible changes. The hydrochars have a spongy, but not ordered porous structure.

3.3. Volatile products detected by Py-GC/MS

3.3.1. Pyrolysis of raw azolla

Py-GC/MS measurements were performed with the aim of detailed analysis of the volatile thermal decomposition products of the samples. The pyrolysis of azolla resulted in a great variety of chemical compounds, as illustrated in Fig. 3a. As many as 137 individual compounds have been identified in the pyrograms, which are listed in Table 2. The relative abundance, molecular mass, and characteristic mass spectral fragment ions of the identified compounds are given in Table S2 of Supplementary data.

The characteristic pyrolysis products of azolla were phenolics, cyclic and acyclic oxygenates from carbohydrates, nitrogen-containing compounds, aromatic and aliphatic hydrocarbons, and phytosterols. Phenolics (phenol (53), cresols (5758)) were the dominant decomposition products. Several dihydroxybenzenes (78,82,83,84) and various phenol derivatives (55,60,61,62,68,73,76) were also detected in the pyrolyzate. Nierop et al. [32] proved that phenolics and dihydroxybenzenes were derived from polyphenols during pyrolysis, and azolla did not contain lignin as reported in several studies. Numerous nitrogen-containing compounds, such as heteroaromatics (pyrroles, pyridine derivatives, polycyclic compounds), cyclic dipeptides (also called 2,5-diketopiperazines, DKPs), and nitriles, were formed due to the relatively high nitrogen (3.0%) and protein content (17.8%) of azolla [30,49]. A few nitrogen-containing heterocyclic compounds, e.g., harmaline (112) and β -carboline (113), can be related to plant alkaloids [50] or chain degradation and cyclization products of proteins

Fig. 2. SEM micrographs (at 2000 × magnification) of (a) raw azolla; of torrefied samples: (b) Tor260, (c) Tor280, (d) Tor300; and of hydrochars: (d) HTC260, (e) HTC280, (f) HTC300.

Fig. 3. Pyrograms acquired at 600 °C: (a) raw azolla, (b) Tor300, and (c) HTC300 samples.

containing tryptophan [51]. The high protein content of azolla also enhanced also the formation of an aromatic hydrocarbon, toluene via the scission of aromatic moieties of amino acid residues (mainly phenylalanine) [52].

A broad hump appeared in the pyrograms in the time range of 40–50 min (Fig. 3), which was resulted from the continuous elution of an unresolved complex mixture. According to the relevant mass spectra, it can be attributed to various forms of lipids (sterolic and acyclic compounds) formed during pyrolysis, as the cracking reactions of larger molecular weight hydrocarbons are promoted above 550 °C [53].

3.3.2. Pyrolysis of torrefied samples

Fig. 3b presents the pyrogram of Tor300 sample in comparison with that of raw azolla (Fig. 3a) illustrating the effect of thermal pretreatment on the volatile composition. The whole series of pyrograms of the torrefied samples is shown in Fig. S2 of Supplementary data. The intensities were normalized to the pyrolyzed sample mass for the better comparison. The major gas peak at the beginning of the pyrograms (2–3 min) was truncated uniformly at the same abundance. The gaseous and vapor compounds of this unresolved peak (e.g., carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide, water, methane and ammonia) were omitted from Table 2 and from the calculations of peak integrals because of the poor resolution.

The pyrolysis products of similar type or origin were grouped together with the aim of providing quantitative information on the changes of yields upon the pretreatments. The yields of the grouped pyrolysis products are illustrated in Fig. 4. The intensity values in percentages can be seen in details in Table S3 of Supplementary data. Each compound was classified to one of the following groups: carbohydrate products, phenols, nitrogen-containing compounds, aromatic hydrocarbons, aliphatic compounds, phytosterols, and a group of other compounds and mixed-type unresolved peaks. The classification of each pyrolysis product is marked with a capital letter in Table 2. As described in the literature [34,54], the lipid content of the azolla extract consists of long-chain alkanols, diols, and its fatty acid esters. In this work, the unidentified compounds of high retention times (127–132,134,136) were classified into the groups of aliphatic compounds or phytosterols according to their assumed molecular structure based on their mass spectra. The relative intensities of the compound

classes in Table S3 and Fig. 4 were calculated from the sum of integral values of the corresponding peaks in the total ion chromatograms. The integral areas were normalized to the pyrolyzed sample amount, and then the numbers were divided by the average area sum of the peak integrals from the pyrogram of raw azolla. In addition, the percentages of the thermally treated samples were multiplied by the mass yield ratio of the pretreatment. Hence, the changes in pyrolyzate yields, due to the thermal pretreatment, became comparable based on the pyrolyzate yield of raw azolla.

In fact, the peak area values do not correspond to the mass yields, because the response factors of the various compounds may differ considerably in the mass spectrometric detector. Nevertheless, the relative area values of the same compounds in different GC/MS chromatograms, taken under the same experimental conditions, correspond to the relative mass yields. It should be noted that the calculated relative intensities represent mainly the composition of the lighter fraction of the pyrolyzate. As it was mentioned above, the gaseous fraction formed during pyrolysis was excluded from the calculation because of the poor resolution. Moreover, the heavy fraction, which is forming also to a remarkable extent during heating [55,56], cannot be measured appropriately by GC/MS. Therefore, the total pyrolyzate yields detected by Py-GC/MS are not representative for the total volatile composition, but the ratio of this lighter fraction can be estimated within the total volatile content, which is determined by proximate analysis. For this reason, Table S3 was supplemented with the row of the percentages of retained volatile contents (on the basis of volatile content of raw azolla) calculated from the data in Table 1.

The fingerprint of the pyrograms was quite similar for all of the raw and torrefied samples (Fig. S2). However, during the pyrolysis of torrefied samples, the yields of acetic acid (10) and levoglucosan (92) were decreasing considerably with increasing torrefaction temperature. They are formed only to a small extent from Tor300 sample. Acetic acid is a typical thermal decomposition product of carbohydrate sources (especially of hemicellulose), and levoglucosan is the monomer of glucan polymers, like cellulose and starch [57]. Thus, the results of pyrolysis of the thermally treated samples suggest that mainly the carbohydrate content was degraded during torrefaction, which is in agreement with the thermogravimetric results. The series of DTG curves (Fig. 1a) shows a decreasing tendency of the major peak as a function of the

Table 2
Pyrolysis products of raw azolla, torrefied samples, and hydrochars detected by Py-GC/MS.

No.	R. t. ^a (min)	Compound	Group ^b	No.	R. t. ^a (min)	Compound	Group ^b
1	2.65	Acetone	O	71	21.89	Methylpyridinol	N
2	2.89	Acetonitrile	N	72	21.95	1,4:3,6-Dianhydro- α -D-glucopyranose	C
3	3.01	2-Methylfuran	C	73	22.50	4-Vinylphenol	P
4	3.33	But-3-en-2-one	C	74	22.82	Pentadecane	L
5		Butan-2-one	C	75	22.88	Pentadecene	L (O)
6		Butan-2,3-dione	C	76		Propoxyphenol	P (O)
7	3.47	Heptane	L	77	23.54	5-Hydroxymethylloxolan-5-one	C (O)
8		Heptene	L	78		Catechol	P (O)
9	3.66	Benzene	A	79	23.63	Indole	N
10	4.83	Acetic acid	O	80	25.17	Methyl-1H-indole	N
11	5.34	Octane	L	81	25.62	Methyl-1H-indole	N
12		Octene	L	82	25.88	Hydroquinone	P
13	5.47	Hydroxyacetone	C	83	26.47	Resorcinol	P
14	5.69	Toluene	A	84	26.67	Dihydroxytoluene	P (O)
15	6.18	Pyridine	N	85		Heptadecane	L (O)
16	6.69	3-Methylbutanenitrile	N	86	26.73	Heptadecene	L
17	7.52	Propanoic acid	O	87	27.33	2,3-Dimethylindole	N
18	7.89	2-Methylpyridine	N	88	27.38	Unidentified branched C ₁₉ alkene	L
19	8.02	Nonane	L	89	27.51	Phthalimide	N
20		Non-1-ene	L	90	29.04	Naphthalene	O
21	8.26	Ethylbenzene	A	91	29.50	Neophytadiene	L
22	8.40	Pyrrole	N	92	30.08	Levogluconan	C
23	8.48	Xylene	A	93	30.16	Nonadecane	L
24	9.13	Furan-3(2H)-one	C	94	30.23	Nonadecene	L
25		3-Furaldehyde	C	95	30.51	Pyrocoll	N
26	9.30	Xylene	A	96	31.05	Methylnaphthalenol	O
27	9.54	Styrene	A	97		Unidentified aliphatic (phytene derivative)	L (O)
28	9.63	2-Hydroxy-3-oxobutanal	C	98		5-Isobutylimidazolidine-2,4-dione	N (O)
29	9.88	Cyclopent-2-en-1-one	C	99	32.76	Palmitonitrile	L
30	9.93	Furfural	C	100	33.17	Cyclo(-Pro-Ala-)	N
31	10.05	4-Methylpentanenitrile	N	101	33.95	Cyclo(-Ala-Leu-)	N (O)
32	10.75	Methyl-1H-pyrrole	N	102		Palmitic acid	L (O)
33	10.91	Methyl-1H-pyrrole	N	103	34.00	Cyclo(-Pro-Ala-)	N
34	11.34	2-Furanmethanol	C	104	34.64	Cyclo(-Pro-Gly-)	N
35	11.52	2-Methylcyclopent-2-en-1-one	C	105	35.04	Pyroglutamic acid derivative	N
36	13.06	2-Hydroxycyclopent-2-en-1-one	C (O)	106	35.24	Cyclo(-Pro-Val-)	N
37		Benzaldehyde	O	107	36.17	Cyclo(-Pro-Leu-)	N
38		Benzofuran	O	108		Cyclo(-Pro-Pro-)	N
39	13.32	Dimethyl-1H-pyrrole	N	109	36.32	Cyclo(-Leu-Leu-)	N
40		Ethyl-1H-pyrrole	N	110	36.69	Cyclo(-Pro-Ile-)	N
41	13.43	Propenylbenzene/Indane	A	111	36.78	Cyclo(-Pro-Ile-)	N
42	13.63	Undecane	L	112	37.25	Harmene	N
43		Undecene	L	113	37.62	β -Carboline	N
44	14.12	3-Methylcyclopent-2-en-1-one	C (O)	114	37.89	Dibenzyl	A (O)
45		Indene	A (O)	115		Unidentified alkanone	L (O)
46	14.44	Furan-2(5H)-one	C	116	38.15	Palmitamide	L
47	14.93	3-Methyl-5-methylidene-furan-2(5H)-one	C	117	40.22	Cyclo(-Phe-Ala-)	N
48	15.57	2,3-Dimethylcyclopent-2-en-1-one	C	118	41.13	Cyclo(-Phe-Val-)	N
49	15.62	2-Hydroxy-3-methylcyclopent-2-en-1-one	C	119		Cyclo(-Pro-Hyp-)	N
50	16.05	Acetophenone	O	120	41.54	Cyclo(-Phe-Gly-)	N
51	16.18	Dodecane	L	121		Cyclo(-Phe-Val-)	N
52		Dodecene	L	122	42.33	Cyclo(-Phe-Leu-)	N
53	16.56	Phenol	P	123	42.70	Cyclo(-Pro-Phe-)	N
54	17.71	<i>o</i> -Cresol	P	124	42.84	Cyclo(-Pro-Phe-)	N
55	18.00	Dimethylphenol	P	125		Cyclo(-Phe-Leu-)	N
56	18.13	Naphthalene	A	126	43.46	Cyclo(-Pro-pyroGlu-)	N
57	18.57	<i>p</i> -Cresol	P	127	43.61	Unidentified aliphatic	L
58		<i>m</i> -Cresol	P	128	44.84	Unidentified aliphatic	L
59	19.11	Phenylacetonitrile	N	129	47.23	Unidentified sterol	S
60	19.64	Dimethylphenol	P	130	47.79	Unidentified aliphatic (and/or sterolic)	L
61	20.49	Dimethylphenol	P	131	47.95	Unidentified sterol	S
62	20.57	4-Ethylphenol	P	132	49.95	Unidentified aliphatic	L
63	20.73	Tetradecane	L	133	50.21	α -Tocopherol	S
64	20.78	Tetradecene	L (O)	134	52.08	Unidentified aliphatic	L
65		Aminophenol	N (O)	135	52.92	Campesterol	S
66	21.27	Succinimide	N	136	55.33	Unidentified aliphatic	L
67		Pyridinol	N	137	55.52	β -Sitossterol	S
68	21.53	Unidentified C ₃ -phenol	P				
69	21.74	3-Phenylpropanenitrile	N (O)				
70		Indan-1-one	O				

^a Retention time.

^b Group of molecule type or supposed origin: C, carbohydrate products; P, phenols; N, nitrogen-containing compounds; A, aromatic hydrocarbons; L, aliphatic compounds; S, phytosterols; O, other compounds and unresolved mixed-type peaks.

Fig. 4. Relative yields of pyrolysis products arranged in compound groups from raw azolla, torrefied samples, and hydrochars. Percentages of the pretreated samples are multiplied by the solid yield of pretreatment for comparison.

torrefaction temperature, as the decomposition of the cellulose/starch content takes place in the range of the applied pretreatment temperatures [57]. The corrected summed yield of the decomposition products of carbohydrates clearly indicates in Fig. 4 that the sources of these volatiles were gradually decomposed at 260–300 °C.

The pyrolysis yields of aliphatic compounds and especially of phytosterols were also smaller from torrefied samples than from the raw biomass (Fig. 4, Table S3). As an example, the aliphatic neophytadiene (91) was present only in the raw sample and it was nearly absent in the torrefied samples (Fig. S2). The formation of this compound can be explained by the thermal decomposition of chlorophyll [58]. The long aliphatic side-chain of chlorophyll molecule is attached with an ester bond to the chlorin ring, and it is supposed to be eliminated as neophytadiene (91) with the formation of a new double bond as observed during the thermal decomposition of terpenoids [59]. Despite of the moderate decrease, more than half of the sum of aliphatic compounds and phytosterols was retained in Tor300 sample (Fig. 4, Table S3), which is an important aspect in terms of the energetic utilization of torrefied biomass.

The results presented in Fig. 4 suggest that the sources of phenols, aromatic hydrocarbons, and nitrogen-containing compounds decomposed just slightly during torrefaction at 260 °C, indicating that these products originate from the thermally more stable parts of azolla. Nevertheless, the yield of nitrogen-containing compounds was reduced significantly in Tor300 sample. The comparison of the sum of corrected relative intensities with the retained volatile contents (last two rows in Table S3) shows that the total pyrolyzate yields were decreased to a smaller extent than the total volatile content from the Tor260 and Tor280 samples. However, the gaseous products were not quantified in the pyrolysis study, so the formation of gases may account for the differences at lower temperatures. Nevertheless, the release of the measured pyrolyzate fraction was more proportional to the total volatile loss at a higher temperature (300 °C).

3.3.3. Pyrolysis of hydrochars

The evaluation of the pyrolysis results of azolla hydrochars was performed similarly as described above for the torrefied samples. The comparison of the pyrograms of HTC300 sample (Fig. 3c) and raw azolla (Fig. 3a) shows that HTC at 300 °C led to a highly reduced intensity or absence of carbohydrate markers in the pyrolyzate (e.g.,

hydroxyacetone (13), hydroxycyclopentenones (36,49), and anhydrosugars (72,92)). HTC260 sample evolved about half amount of levoglucosan than raw azolla (Fig. S3). However, the carbohydrate content was reduced especially in HTC280 and HTC300 samples, where the amount of levoglucosan (92) was close to the detection limit. This observation suggests that the carbohydrate components of azolla were degraded to a high extent during hydrothermal carbonization.

The pyrolysis of the hydrochars produced significantly smaller amounts of hydroquinone (82) and nitrogen-containing compounds, such as indole (79), methylindole (80), succinimide (66), and nitriles (2,16,31,59,99). These compounds originated from those components of the biomass, which are thermally more stable than the carbohydrate content and decomposed above 350 °C according to the DTG curves (Fig. 1b). Our results are in agreement with the conclusion of Olszewski et al. [60], who studied brewer's spent grains by Py-GC/MS after HTC pretreatment. They suggested that Maillard reaction occurred between the carbohydrate and protein contents of brewer's spent grains during HTC resulting in smaller yields of nitrogen-containing compounds during the subsequent pyrolysis. Minor yield of nitriles can also be related to hydrolytic reactions taking place during hydrothermal carbonization [10]. Some aromatic hydrocarbons (e.g., toluene (14), ethylbenzene (21), styrene (27), and indene (45)) and oxygenated compounds (e.g., benzaldehyde (37), benzofuran (38), and naphthalenol (90)) were produced in higher amounts especially from the samples carbonized at higher temperatures.

The summed and corrected percentages of the pyrolyzate yields of hydrochar samples are shown in Fig. 4 and Table S3. In accordance with the above discussed observations, the carbohydrate, sterolic, aliphatic, and protein contents were decomposed considerably during the hydrothermal carbonization. The sources of phytosterols were diminished especially in HTC300 hydrochar; however, very low phytosterol yield was detected from the HTC260 and HTC280 samples, as well. Although the sources of phenols and aromatic hydrocarbons were degraded also to a remarkable extent during HTC, the relative ratio of these decomposition products increased within the pyrolyzates of hydrochars. The comparison of total intensities of the detected compounds with the corrected volatile content (last two rows in Table S3) shows that the sources of the measured pyrolyzate fraction in azolla decreased proportionally with the overall volatile content during the hydrothermal carbonization at each temperature applied.

Fig. 5. (a) Score plot and (b) loading plot of PCA based on the pyrolyzate compositions of raw azolla, torrefied samples, and hydrochars from Py-GC/MS measurements.

The decreased intensity of several chromatographic peaks in the pyrograms of hydrochars (Fig. S3) comparing to the pyrograms of torrefied samples (Fig. S2) demonstrate that the wet process had higher impact on the composition of biomass than torrefaction, which is in accordance with the thermogravimetric data. Fig. 4 illustrates that HTC at 260 °C decreased the total volatile content of azolla at a somewhat higher extent than torrefaction at 300 °C.

The intensity of carbohydrate products was decreased gradually by 30, 60, and 80% in the pyrograms of torrefied samples with increasing torrefaction temperatures (260, 280, and 300 °C, respectively). The reduction is much higher for the HTC samples; the relative yield of carbohydrate products was reduced by 70% in the pyrolyzate of HTC260, while only traces of carbohydrates remained in the pyrograms of HTC280 and HTC300 samples.

The ratio of phytosterols was decreased to the highest extent during both treatments: Tor260 sample evolved about 50%, while HTC260 released only 10% phytosterols in comparison with raw azolla. Nevertheless, some β -sitosterol remained in the samples after each treatment. It is probable that phytosterols of lower vapor pressure were prone to evaporate from the samples during both treatments. The ratio of aliphatic products decreased only to a small extent in the pyrolyzate of torrefied samples, while HTC strongly reduced the source of these pyrolysis products. It is likely that fatty acid esters were hydrolyzed during the hydrothermal carbonization, while they were thermally stable at the torrefaction temperatures (up to 300 °C). Neophytadiene (91) was not present in any hydrochar pyrolyzates, indicating that it had been released during HTC, similarly to torrefaction.

The sources of aromatic products are the thermally most stable parts of azolla during both torrefaction and HTC as the intensities of aromatic hydrocarbons and phenols indicate in Fig. 4. The next most stable components of azolla are the sources of nitrogen-containing compounds. The relative yield of nitrogen-containing pyrolysis products was decreased only slightly from the samples torrefied at moderate temperatures, but it reduced by almost half in the pyrolyzate of Tor300 sample. On the other hand, the effect of HTC is much higher; the yield of nitrogen-containing product decreased by more than 50% from HTC260 sample and further reduced at higher HTC temperature.

3.3.4. Principal component analysis

The pyrolyzate compositions of the raw azolla, torrefied samples, and hydrochars were analyzed by PCA. First, the input data of the detected decomposition products were reduced to some extent by grouping the compounds to more specific categories than it was used in Table 2. The following compound groups were formed according to the structural similarities: alkylnitriles (2,16,31), aryl nitriles (59,99), cyclo-

C₅ (cyclopentenoids; 29,35,48,49), furans (3,24,25,30,34,46,47), anhydrosugars (72,92), benzenoids (benzene, alkyl-, and alkenylbenzenes; 9,21,23,26,27,41,56), toluene (14), phenol (53), cresols (54,57,58), phenolics (alkyl- and alkenylphenols; 55,60–62, 68,73,82,83), C₇–C₁₁ aliphatics (7,8,11,12,19,20,42,43,), C₁₂–C₂₀ aliphatics (51,52,63,64,74,75,85,86,88,91,93,94), C₂₀₊ unidentified aliphatics (127,128,130,132,134,136), palmitamide (116), pyridins and pyrrols (15,18,22,32,33,39,40,66,67,71,79–81,87,89,112,113), DKPs (95,100,101,103–111,117–126), sterols (129,131,133,135,137), small oxygenates (1,4–6,10,13,17,28), and aromatic oxygenates (50,90). The unresolved peaks with mixed-type compounds were omitted from the calculations. The major pyrolysis products (i.e., toluene, phenol, cresols) were treated as separated inputs due to their significant contributions.

The first two principal components of the data set explain almost 82% of the total variance. The score plot of the first and the second factors shows in Fig. 5a that the treated samples are separated significantly according to type of the thermal treatments (torrefaction or HTC). While the torrefied samples are ordered into a line shape starting from the point of the raw sample, the position of the hydrochars indicates that the wet media brought on different decomposition and reaction pathways. It can be established that the first factor correlates with the severity of the pretreatment. The position of the hydrochars and torrefied samples indicates that HTC caused more severe decomposition than torrefaction. The torrefied samples and hydrochars are separated along the second factor, indicating the different effect of HTC and torrefaction. The loading plot in Fig. 5b shows that the major contributors of the first principal component are typical carbohydrate decomposition products (i.e., anhydrosugars, cyclopentenoids, furans, small oxygenates) and aromatics (aromatic hydrocarbons and oxygenates). Regarding the latter compound group, cresols are closer to toluene than to phenol or other phenolics, suggesting that the formation of cresols proceeded via similar route as the formation of toluene during the pyrolysis of the samples.

4. Conclusions

The thermal decomposition of raw azolla as well as torrefied and hydrothermally carbonized solid products formed at the same temperatures was studied by TGA and Py-GC/MS techniques in order to reveal the effects of dry and wet thermal treatments on azolla biomass.

The comparison of torrefied and HTC treated azolla samples revealed, that HTC process resulted in a significantly higher degree of decomposition than torrefaction at the same temperatures. Based on both TGA and Py-GC/MS results, torrefaction at 300 °C degraded the

sample somewhat less than HTC at 260 °C. Significant amount of inorganic material was dissolved during HTC, while the ash content was practically unchanged during torrefaction. TGA showed that mostly the thermally less stable carbohydrate components of azolla degraded during torrefaction, while the decomposition behavior of the residue did not change. The DTG curves indicated that the torrefied samples contained a negligible amount of substances of lower thermal stability up to 250–280 °C, while the decomposition of hydrochars started at much lower temperatures (below 200 °C). SEM images revealed more intense morphological changes as a result of HTC comparing to torrefaction. Tor260 and Tor280 samples visibly kept the main structure of biomass, while hydrochars and Tor300 have a porous structure.

The analysis of the pyrolysis products showed that the sources of aromatic products were the thermally most stable parts of azolla during both torrefaction and HTC. The yield of nitrogen-containing compounds only slightly reduced in the pyrolyzate of Tor260 and Tor280 samples; however, the sources of these compounds were significantly eliminated during hydrothermal carbonization of azolla. The intensity of carbohydrate products was decreased gradually with increasing treatment temperatures in the pyrograms of torrefied samples; however, HTC reduced strongly the carbohydrate content of the samples. While levoglucosan was still present in the pyrolyzate of HTC260 sample, its carbohydrate sources were decomposed to a large extent at higher temperatures of the wet pretreatment. The amount of phytosterols decreased to the greatest extent during both treatments, only 2 and 27% of the original phytosterol content remained in the HTC300 and Tor300 samples, respectively. The aliphatic compounds were mainly preserved after torrefaction, while HTC strongly decreased the sources of these products, which can be explained by hydrolysis of fatty acid esters. PCA analysis of the Py-GC/MS results showed that the pyrolyzate compositions of the various samples differed significantly depending on the temperature and type of pretreatment (HTC or torrefaction). The data processing verified that HTC resulted in more severe decomposition than torrefaction at all studied temperatures.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Bence Babinszki: Investigation, Writing - original draft, Validation, Visualization. **Emma Jakob:** Supervision, Writing - review & editing. **Zoltán Sebestyén:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Marianne Blazsó:** Writing - review & editing. **Bernadett Berényi:** Investigation. **Jitendra Kumar:** Investigation. **Bhavya B. Krishna:** Writing - review & editing. **Thallada Bhaskar:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition. **Zsuzsanna Czégény:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing - review & editing, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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